

Reactions of Metal Alkoxides with β -Diketones and β -Ketoesters*

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A INTRODUCTION

1 History

METAL β -diketonates are amongst the most widely studied coordination compounds and their chemistry has been investigated for almost all metals and metalloids in the periodic table. The coordination tendency of β -diketones is now well established and a large number of more potential ligands, being synthesised by organic chemists every year, are used to prepare new complexes with metals to elucidate with greater clarity the nature of bonding, etc and to develop newer applications of the same.

The chemistry of metal β -diketonates in a sense reflects the different eras in the development of inorganic chemistry as a whole¹. Starting with the synthesis of these derivatives for the first time in 1887 by Combes², the nature of bonding was elucidated by the classical work of Werner³ in 1890's followed later by studies by Morgan⁴ and Sidgwick⁵ in 1920's and their coworkers who drew attention to the predominant chelating character of these ligands. A new dimension was added to the understanding about the nature of bonding in these derivatives by Calvin and Wilson⁶, who in 1945 suggested the presence of aromaticity in β -diketonate rings, this aspect of work has been later pursued by Collman⁷ and others. With increasing applications of sophisticated instrumental techniques for the structural determination, the classical work of Cotton and Holm⁸ in 1958 on trimeric nickel bis(acetylacetonate) opened a new chapter in this field. The work of Lewis and coworkers⁹ during sixties has further demonstrated a new type of bonding mode of these ligands with some metals like platinum etc. A new chapter in the field of a closely allied series of derivatives was introduced in 1969 by Chaston and Livingstone¹⁰ who investigated a series of metal thio- β -diketonates by replacing carbonyl oxygens of β -diketones with sulfur atoms. Since then, a large number of metal monothio- and dithio- β -diketonates have been synthesised and their properties have been studied.

Apart from the theoretical importance of the topic, multifarious practical applications in analytical operations and other industrial uses have led to a rapid development in the field of metal β -diketonates, which can be discerned by the publication of more than 1500 papers during the last two decades on different aspects of the chemistry of these complexes.

II Classification of metal β -diketonates

Metal β -diketonates may be classified into following three categories depending upon the mode of bonding of ligand moieties with metal atoms.

- (i) Oxygen bonded β -diketonato complexes,
- (ii) Carbon bonded β -diketonato complexes,
- (iii) Both Carbon and Oxygen bonded β -diketonato complexes

(i) Oxygen bonded β -diketonato complexes

In these derivatives, β -ketoenolate anion acts as an unidentate ligand, e.g. in $\text{Me}_2\text{Si}(\text{acac})_2$,

or as bidentate ligand which is the usual mode of bonding of β -diketones with most of the metals of the periodic table, e.g., $\text{Cl}_2\text{Si}(\text{acac})_2$:

(ii) Carbon bonded β -diketonato complexes

In β -diketonato complexes of sulphur, selenium, tellurium, mercury, platinum and gold, the ligand carbonyl groups do not appear to participate in bonding, e.g., $\text{Se}(\text{acac})_2$ may be represented as

(iii) Both Carbon and Oxygen bonded β -diketonato complexes

In some β -diketonate complexes of platinum, e.g., $\text{PtCl}(\text{acac})_2$, one of the ligand moieties is bonded to platinum via both carbonyl oxygen atoms while the other moiety is bonded through the 3-carbon atom only.

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These stable complexes are generally coloured and soluble in common organic solvents

III Uses

The tendency of these β -diketone ligands to form inner coordination compounds with a variety of metals provided the inorganic chemists with a large number of derivatives which at one time could be considered as rare examples of electropositive metals in combinations depicting the characteristics of covalent compounds i.e., volatility and solubility in organic solvents. These special characteristics of metal β -diketonates have been used in solvent extraction studies of various metal ions. Exceptional volatility of derivatives with fluorinated β -diketones has been exploited increasingly in gas chromatographic separations of metals.

A novel application of some lanthanide β -diketonates in structural elucidation of organic compounds by P.M.R. technique was discovered by Hinckley¹¹ for the first time in 1969. Since then, a wide variety of applications have been described for these complexes, termed under the general name of 'lanthanide shift reagents'¹². The application of $\text{Cr}(\text{acac})_3$ has recently been shown by Gansow *et al*¹³ in a better resolution of C-13 N.M.R. spectra also of some metal carbonyls.

Since the first publication by Lempicki and Samelson¹⁴ on their laser activity, considerable work has been carried out on such properties of β -diketonates, particularly of europium.

B. A BRIEF RESUME OF WORK CARRIED OUT IN OUR LABORATORIES

1. Reactions of metal alkoxides with β -diketones and β -ketoesters

The marked reactivity of metal alkoxides towards any organic reagent having a hydroxy group led us to look into the reactions of metal alkoxides on the β -diketones, β -ketoesters and allied reagents. As most of this work was carried out in the laboratories of the University of Rajasthan, where this annual meeting of the Indian Chemical Society is being held, I thought it appropriate to describe the same briefly on this occasion. A large number of novel derivatives with metals depicting uncommon coordination numbers have been synthesised during the course of this work, but it has not been possible to elucidate or confirm their structural details fully due to lack of sophisticated physico-chemical techniques, the present account, I hope, would, therefore,

indicate a rich field of research for further structural determination by coordination chemists.

As indicated above, metal alkoxides depict marked reactivity towards any reagent with a hydroxy group. The β -diketones as well as β -ketoesters are well known to show tautomerism, the enol form of which generally has a hydroxy group available for reaction. These reagents, therefore, depict a very facile reactivity towards metal alkoxides, in which the alkoxy group is replaced by the enolate form of the β -diketonate or β -ketoester reagent. The reactions of titanium alkoxides with β -diketones and β -ketoester in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios were investigated by Schmidt¹⁵ and the *mono*- and *bis*-derivatives thus isolated were both assigned hexacoordinated structures which were later supported by cryoscopic molecular weight study¹⁶. Contrary to the above, Yamamoto and Kambara¹⁷ assumed 5- and 6-coordinated structures for the *mono*- and *bis*-derivatives respectively on the basis of infra red studies. These workers did not observe any replacement beyond the formation of *bis*-derivatives, the hydrolysis of *bis*-derivative led to the formation of titanyl *bis*(acetylacetonate). Mehrotra and coworkers¹⁸⁻²¹ studied in detail the reactions of titanium alkoxides with β -diketones, fluoro- β -diketones, and β -ketoesters in 1:1 and 1:2 molar ratios and *mono*- as well as *bis*-chelates were obtained, respectively. In order to explore the possibility of further replacement, a reaction of dialkoxide *bis*(acetylacetonate) with excess of acetylacetone was carried out and it was observed that the reaction was quite slow, yet the third alkoxy group was replaced, but the *tris*(acetylacetonate) derivative thus formed decomposed instantaneously to give titanyl *bis*(acetylacetonate). Compared to the non-volatile nature of β -diketonates, the corresponding fluoro- β -diketonates of titanium are more volatile products and could be distilled *in vacuo*.

Fay *et al*^{22,23} have assigned the *trans*-configuration for hexacoordinated *bis*(acetylacetonate) derivatives of titanium. Nevertheless Bradley and Holloway^{24,25} on the basis of P.M.R. studies on these derivatives ruled out the possibility of *trans*-configuration in favour of *cis*-configuration. These workers found that all the products of type $\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_2\text{X}_2$ exist only in *cis* form (optically active) over a wide temperature range. Activation energies for intramolecular exchange of ligands in these functional molecules showed that steric hindrance of the alkoxy group increased the energy of activation, but did not promote the formation of the *trans* form.

Following the investigations with titanium alkoxides, the reactions of a large number of metal alkoxides (generally ethoxides or isopropoxides) with β -diketones and β -ketoesters have been carried out in our laboratories. These reactions can be represented by the following general equations

(R=Et and Prⁱ)

In general, the metal alkoxide is mixed with a stoichiometric amount of the desired ligand in benzene medium and after fractionation of the benzene-alcohol azeotrope, the corresponding β -diketonate or β -ketoester derivative can be isolated by removal of excess benzene by evaporation²⁶. The advantage of this method is that the complexes having different apparent coordination numbers can be readily syn-

thesised using the desired stoichiometric ratio of the ligand.

In the following paragraphs is being described a brief summary of the reactions studied in our laboratory, in the form of general equations, indicating the formation of metal chelates of varying coordination numbers employing different stoichiometric ratios of the reactants :

(R=Et, Prⁱ, R'=R''=CH₃; R'=CH₃, R''=C₆H₅; R'=CH₃, R''=OC₂H₅, n=1-3)²⁷.

(R'=R''=CH₃; R'=CH₃, R''=OCH₃; R'=CH₃, R''=OC₂H₅, n=1-3)²⁸.

(R=Et, Prⁱ, n=1, 2; R'=R''=CH₃; R'=CH₃, R''=C₆H₅; R'=R''=CF₃, R'=CF₃, R''=C₆F₅; R'=CH₃, R''=OCH₃; R'=CH₃, R''=OC₂H₅)¹⁹⁻²¹.

↓ decomposed

(R' = R'' = CH₃, R' = R'' = CF₃, R' = CH₃, R'' = C₆H₅, R' = CH₃, R'' = OCH₃, n = 1-4)^{29,30}.

(M = Nb, Ta, n = 1-3, R' = R'' = CH₃, R' = CH₃, R'' = C₆H₅, R' = R'' = C₆H₅, R' = CH₃, R'' = OCH₃; R' = CH₃, R'' = OC₂H₅)³¹⁻³⁴.

(R' = R'' = CH₃, R' = CH₃, R'' = C₆H₅, R' = R'' = C₆H₅, n = 1, 2)³⁵.

(R = Et, ⁻Bu, n = 1, 2 when R' = CH₃, R'' = C₆H₅ and R' = R'' = C₆H₅, n = 1-3 when R' = R'' = CH₃)³⁶.

(R' = R'' = CH₃, R' = CH₃, R'' = C₆H₅, R' = CH₃, R'' = OCH₃, n = 1, 2)³⁷.

(R' = R'' = CH₃; R' = CH₃, R'' = C₆H₅; R' = CH₃, R'' = OCH₃)³⁷.

II Some Salient Results from this work

For the benefit of my younger friends continuing to struggle in ill-equipped laboratories even now, I would crave your indulgence in pointing out that with the penetrating insight of my young students and coworkers, we could, during the course of these investigations, correct some long standing errors which had crept even in undergraduate textbooks on the supposed trimeric structure of titanium as well as tin dichloride *bis*(acetylacetonate) and we were also successful in the synthesis of anhydrous β -diketonates of lanthanide elements, for which quite a few unsuccessful and doubtful efforts had been published in the literature earlier

Our first publication in the field of mixed metal alkoxide β -diketonates was on the synthesis of titanium diethoxide *bis*(acetylacetonate) which was found to be monomeric in a number of organic solvents³⁸. This led us to some doubts on the reported molecular complexity of titanium dichloride *bis*(acetylacetonate), synthesised in the beginning of this century independently by Rosenheim³⁹ and Dilthey⁴⁰. This product was assigned an ionic structure of type $[\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_3]_2^+ [\text{TiCl}_6]^{2-}$, which is the trimeric form of $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{acac})_2$ merely on the basis of analogy with the product $\text{Si}(\text{acac})_3\text{Cl}\cdot\text{HCl}$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{acac})_3\text{Cl}$, obtained earlier in the corresponding reactions of acetylacetone with silicon or zirconium tetrachlorides. The only evidence adduced in support of the above structure was that the product on treatment with ferric chloride gave a product of the composition $[\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_3][\text{FeCl}_4]$, the formation of which could be easily explained on the basis of the following plausible reaction

On repeating the experimental work of Rosenheim and Dilthey, the analytical results of the products obtained did correspond to $\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_2\text{Cl}_2$ and $[\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_3][\text{FeCl}_4]$. However, on actual measurements of the molecular weights of the derivative $\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_2\text{Cl}_2$ in a number of common organic solvents, the observed experimental value was found to correspond to the simple monomeric $\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_2\text{Cl}_2$. Further the derivative was found to be a non-electrolyte in these solvents, thereby ruling out the possibility of the above trimeric formation $[\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_3]_2^+ [\text{TiCl}_6]^{2-}$, as suggested earlier

The product of the reaction between titanium tetrachloride and excess of acetylacetone was, thus, shown to be a simple hexa-coordinated derivative $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{acac})_2$. This was also in conformity with a considerable amount of work on the reactions of titanium tetrachloride with reagents having active hydroxy groups like alcohols⁴¹, and carboxylic acids⁴² in which two of the four chlorine atoms on

titanium tetrachloride were shown to be much more reactive

The formation of the product $[\text{Ti}(\text{acac})_3][\text{FeCl}_4]$ from the reaction of $\text{TiCl}_2(\text{acac})_2$ and FeCl_3 has been shown to be much more complicated and efforts have been made to elucidate it in a number of publications^{38, 43, 44}

In the reaction of stannic chloride with acetylacetone in chloroform at room temperature, we isolated a product of composition $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{acacH}$ which was found to be stable even upto 60-70 under 0.1 mm pressure, but decomposed above 90-100 to give stannic dichloride *bis*(acetylacetonate) as follows⁴⁵

Stannic dichloride *bis*(acetylacetonate) has been prepared alternatively by refluxing stannic chloride and acetylacetone in benzene or chloroform and it also been shown to be a monomeric covalent compound⁴⁵

In still another field the simple technique of the reactions of metal alkoxides with β -diketones and β -ketoesters appears to have provided a very convenient route for the preparation of anhydrous lanthanide derivatives for the first time in 1965. Earlier methods used for the preparation of lanthanide *tris*- β -diketonates were examined critically by Pope *et al*⁴⁷ and by Moeller *et al*⁴⁸ who have conclusively established that the products from aqueous solutions were invariably hydrates, from which generally hydroxy derivatives were obtained on dehydration even under mild conditions. Attempts have been made to synthesize these derivatives in non-aqueous media also by (i) the reaction of lanthanon metal with excess acetylacetone using metal evaporation technique⁴⁹ or (ii) by the reaction of lanthanide hydrides^{50, 51} with excess acetylacetone in the presence of acetic acid. Lis and Bos⁵² have very recently claimed to have isolated a crystalline *tris*-chelate by the former method, yet according to their own description, unusual properties like large number of extra peaks in infra-red spectra, low m_p (94) and observed loss in weight when the derivatives are exposed to air, probably indicate the presence of some volatile fractions in their products which might have been formed in the side-decomposition reactions earlier

Employing lanthanide alkoxides as the starting materials, we have been able to synthesise in our laboratory in 1965, pure *tris*-acetylacetonates of lanthanum⁵³ praseodymium⁵⁴ and neodymium⁵⁵. The lanthanide *isopropoxides* interchange their *isopropoxy* groups with β -diketones and β -ketoesters in different molar ratios to yield mixed as well as *tris*-chelates

(Ln = La³⁺, Pr³⁺, Gd³⁺, Er³⁺, Y³⁺, Yb³⁺, R' = R'' = CH₃, R' = CH₃, R'' = C₆H₅, R' = R'' = C₆H₅; R' = CH₃, R'' = OCH₃; R' = CH₃, R'' = OC₂H₅, n = 1, 2)

These *tris*-β-diketonates have been shown to be dimeric products, which are not as highly hygroscopic as the products claimed earlier as anhydrous *tris*-derivatives. A plausible explanation of this has been offered recently by the author.⁵⁷

For example, the dihydrates Y(acac)₃·(OH₂)₂ and La(acac)₃·(OH₂)₂ have been shown^{58,59} to depict an octa-coordinate positions on the square face of the antiprism :

Fig. 1. Structure of Ln(acac)₃·(OH₂)₂ unit.

Mere removal of the two water molecules under as mild conditions as possible to avoid hydrolysis would probably leave an open unaltered structure with two coordination sites vacant. This explains the extremely hygroscopic nature of such dehydrated products as to make their handling even for any physico-chemical measurements very difficult without rehydration. It may be interesting that the anhydrous dimeric products obtained in our laboratories through the alkoxides are fairly stable to atmospheric structure and one of the plausible structures which can be assigned to them could be of the type⁶¹ shown in Fig. 2 in which two square anti-prisms share one square face :

Fig. 2. A plausible structure of dimeric anhydrous [Ln(acac)₃]₂.

C. Acknowledgements

Before I close, it is my pleasant duty to thank all the younger co-workers and colleagues whose work has been presented by me in this presidential address.

Let me also take advantage of this opportunity of conveying my grateful thanks to all the fellow chemists who did me the great honour of electing me the President of our Indian Chemical Society. I am also thankful to all the fellows, office-bearers and the administrative staff of the Society for the cooperation which I received in the discharge of my duties as the President of the Society.

References

1. R. C. MEHROTRA, R. BOHRA and D. P. GAUR, 'Metal β-Diketonates and Allied Derivatives', Academic Press, London, (In Press).
2. A. COMBES, *Ann. Chim.*, 1897, **12**, 199; *Compt. Rend.*, 1967, **105**, 869.
3. A. WERNER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 2584.
4. G. T. MORGAN and F. H. BURTSALL, "Inorganic Chemistry—A Survey of Modern Developments", W. Heffer & Sons Ltd., Cambridge, U. K., 1936.
5. N. V. SIDGWICK, "The Chemical Elements and their Compounds", Oxford University Press, London, U. K., 1950.
6. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2003.
7. J. P. COLLMAN, R. A. MOSS, S. D. GOLDBY and W. S. TRHANSVOSKY, *Chemistry and Industry*, 1960, 1213.
8. F. A. COTTON and R. H. HOLM, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 5658.
9. G. ALLEN, J. LEWIS, R. F. LONG and C. OLDHAM, *Nature*, 1964, **202**, 590.
10. S. H. H. CHASTON and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 111.
11. C. C. HINCKLEY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 5160.
12. R. E. SIEVERS, ed., 'Nuclear Magnetic Shift Reagents', Academic Press, N. Y., 1973.
13. O. A. GANSOW, A. R. BURKE and W. D. VERNON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 2250.
14. A. LEMPICKI and H. SAMELSON, *Phys. Lett.*, 1963, **4**, 133.
15. F. SCHMIDT, *Angew Chem.*, 1952, **64**, 536; U. S. Patent, 2,680,108, (1954).
16. R. E. REEVES and L. W. MAZZENO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2533.
17. A. YAMAMOTO and S. KAMBARA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4344.

18. D. M. PURI and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1961, **3**, 253.
19. D. M. PURI, K. C. PANDE and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1962, **4**, 393.
20. D. M. PURI and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 499.
21. P. C. BHARARA, V. D. GUPTA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1975, **5**, 59.
22. R. C. FAY and R. N. LOWRY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 1512.
23. N. SERPONE and R. C. FAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 1835.
24. D. C. BRADLEY and C. E. HOLLOWAY, *Chem. Commun.*, 1965, 284.
25. D. C. BRADLEY and C. E. HOLLOWAY, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)* 1969, 282.
26. D. C. BRADLEY, D. P. GAUR and R. C. MEHROTRA, 'Metal Alkoxides', Academic Press, London, 1977.
27. R. K. MEHROTRA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 795.
28. R. C. MEHROTRA and S. R. BINDAL, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 2661.
29. U. B. SAXENA, A. K. RAI, V. K. MATHUR, R. C. MEHROTRA and D. RADFORD, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970 904.
30. P. C. BHARARA, V. D. GUPTA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 725.
31. R. C. MEHROTRA and P. N. KAPOOR, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1964, **7**, 453.
32. R. C. MEHROTRA and P. N. KAPOOR, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1964, **7**, 176.
33. P. N. KAPOOR and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1965, **8**, 339.
34. R. C. MEHROTRA, P. N. KAPOOR, S. PRAKASH and P. N. KAPOOR, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1966, **19**, 2079.
35. V. D. GUPTA, "The University of Rajasthan Studies in Science", Jaipur, 1968, p. 41.
36. D. P. GAUR, G. SRIVASTAVA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 399.
37. R. C. MEHROTRA, and V. D. GUPTA, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 237.
38. K. C. PANDE and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Chemistry and Industry*, 1958, 1198.
39. A. ROSENHEIM, L. LOWENSTAMM and L. SINGER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1833.
40. W. DILTNEY, *Chem. Ber.*, 1964, **37**, 589.
41. J. S. JENNINGS, W. WARDLAW and W. J. R. WAY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 637.
42. K. C. PANDE and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Chemistry and Industry*, 1957, 114.
43. D. M. PURI and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1961, **3**, 247.
44. D. M. PURI, K. C. PANDE and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1962, **4**, 481.
45. R. C. MEHROTRA and V. D. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 911.
46. G. T. MORGAN and H. D. K. DREW, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924 **125**, 372.
47. G. W. POPE, J. F. STEINBACK and W. F. WAGNER, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, **20**, 304.
48. T. MOELLER, D. F. MARTIN, L. C. THOMPSON, R. FERRUS, G. R. FEISTAL and W. J. RANDALL, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **65**, 1.
49. J. R. BLACKBOROW, C. R. EADY, E. A. K. VON GUSTORF, A. SERVANTE and O. WOLFBEIS, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1976, **108**, C32.
50. J. M. KOECHLER and W. G. BOS, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.* 1967, **3**, 545.
51. J. K. PRZYSTAL, W. G. BOS and J. B. LIS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 679.
52. J. B. LIS and W. G. BOS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 443.
53. R. C. MEHROTRA, T. N. MISRA and S. N. MISRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 525.
54. S. N. MISRA, T. N. MISRA and R. C. MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 372.
55. R. C. MEHROTRA and J. M. BATWARA, Proc. 8th Rare Earth Res. Conf., 1968, 771.
56. R. C. MEHROTRA and U. D. Tripathi, Chem. Sym. Punjab Univ. Chandigarh, 1969.
57. R. C. MEHROTRA, Coordination Chemistry of Lanthanides with emphasis on derivatives with Ln-O-C bonds—a special lecture delivered at XVIIIth International Conference on Coordination Chemistry held at Sao Paulo, Brazil in July, 1977.
58. J. A. CUNNINGHAM, D. E. SANDS and W. F. WAGNER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 499.
59. T. PHILLIPS, D. E. SANDS and W. F. WAGNER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 2295.